

LEVEL OF E-COMPETENCE AND ASSOCIATED FACTORS AMONG UNDERGRADUATE NURSING STUDENTS IN KARACHI, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Background

E-competence has become essential for academic achievement and continuous learning, particularly in health-related disciplines like nursing. Despite its importance, there is a lack of research exploring level of E-competence relates to academic motivation and lifelong learning among nursing students.

Objectives: To assess the level of E-competence and its associated factors among undergraduate nursing students in Karachi, Pakistan.

Material and Methods

A cross-sectional analytical study was conducted among undergraduate nursing students in Dow Institute of Nursing and Midwifery, DUHS Karachi. The study duration was four months from March 2025 to June 2025 and study population was all undergraduate nursing students enrolled in Bachelor of Nursing. A total of 384 nursing students were recruited through purposive sampling technique. Inclusion criteria: All nursing students from Year I to Year IV and willing to consent in the study. Exclusion criteria: Who were absent at the time of data collection. Data was collected using a well-structured, self-administered questionnaire. The questionnaire comprised two sections: 1) Demographic Information. 2) Level of E-Competence. Data was analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.

Results:

The present study found that nearly half (44.8%) of the nursing students exhibited a low level of E-competence with mean domain scores of knowledge 47.4%, skills 45.3%, and attitude 41.7%. Factors like age, gender, year of study, and digital literacy training were significantly (p -value < 0.05) associated with E-competence levels. Moreover, older students, males, advanced-year students, and those with digital literacy training showed higher E-competence.

Conclusion: Undergraduate nursing students showed low e-competence in knowledge, skills, and attitudes. Higher competence was associated with older age, male gender, senior year of study, and prior digital literacy training.

Introduction

The integration of digital technology into healthcare has transformed the knowledge and skills requirements of modern nurses. The competence in the use of electronic tools, referred to as e-competence or digital competence, is now considered essential for nursing students as it supports clinical decision-making, communication, and professional growth (1). E-competence encompasses knowledge, technical abilities, and professional attitudes that enable nursing students to engage effectively with electronic health records, e-learning platforms, and telehealth systems (2). Digital competence also plays a direct role in enhancing academic motivation. Students with stronger digital skills engage more actively with course content, collaborate effectively, and make better use of online resources (3). These competencies support lifelong learning by enabling nurses to adapt to technological innovations and evidence-based practice. Ibrahim and Aldawsari (2023) confirmed a positive association between digital competence and student performance in hybrid learning environments (4). Despite these benefits, many nursing students continue to face challenges in developing digital skills due to inadequate training opportunities and limited access to technology (5). Garzón-Artacho et al. (2021) also reported that low digital competence can hinder participation in online courses that require collaboration through digital platforms (6). The COVID-19 pandemic further accelerated the adoption of online and blended learning in nursing education. The students in Pakistan experienced a sudden shift to virtual platforms, requiring rapid acquisition of digital literacy and adaptation to e-learning systems (7). While this transition created opportunities to enhance technological skills, it also revealed variations in knowledge, skills, and attitudes toward digital tools, influenced by infrastructure limitations, faculty readiness, and individual motivation (8). In Pakistan, the rapid digitalization of healthcare institutions has emphasized the need for nurses to demonstrate competence in using electronic

health systems. Tertiary care hospitals increasingly rely on electronic records and reporting tools, yet gaps remain in training and assessment of nursing students. Limited integration of informatics education in curricula may restrict the development of essential e-competence (9). Although international studies highlight the importance of digital competence, local evidence remains scarce, particularly in Karachi, Pakistan. Assessing e-competence and its associated factors among nursing students is therefore crucial for identifying gaps and guiding curriculum development. By evaluating knowledge, skills, and attitudes, this study provides insights that can inform nursing education policies and prepare graduates for a digitally driven healthcare system.

Methodology

A cross-sectional analytical study design was used to assess digital competence among undergraduate nursing students. The study was conducted at Dow Institute of Nursing and Midwifery, Dow University Health Sciences, Karachi (DUHS), Pakistan. The study duration was four months from March 2025 to June 2025 and study population was all undergraduate nursing students enrolled in Bachelor of Nursing. A total of 384 nursing students were recruited through purposive sampling technique. Inclusion criteria: All nursing students from Year I to Year IV and willing to consent in the study. Exclusion criteria: Who were absent at the time of data collection. "The sample size was calculated using Cochran's formula for categorical data at a 95% confidence level with a 5% margin of error. Assuming a population proportion of 0.5, the calculated sample size was 384 nursing students. Before data collection, an approval was obtained from Institutional Review Board of DUHS (Ref: IRB-3149/DUHS/Approval/2024/232) and also informed consent was obtained from each participant. The questionnaires were distributed in classrooms and collected on the same day to ensure maximum participation. Data were collected using a structured, self-administered questionnaire developed after

reviewing validated tools on digital competence and adapted to the nursing context (9,10,11,12). The questionnaire comprised two sections: 1) Demographic Information: age, gender, year of study, and digital literacy training. 2) Level of E-Competence: it has further three domains: i) Knowledge domain: 03 items assessing awareness of digital platforms, privacy, and professional guidelines. ii) Skills domain: 03 items assessing ability to search, evaluate, and use digital tools effectively. iii) Attitudes domain: 06 items assessing perceptions and confidence in digital technology for learning and communication. All items were rated on a five-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). The knowledge & skills score (Items 3-6): total 6-30 points. The attitude score (Items 3-6): 6-30 points. Total Score: 12-60 points. Level of E-competence was measured through scores. It ranges from 12-24 = low E-competence, score ranges from 25-42 = moderate E-competence, score ranges between 43-60 = high E-competence. The questionnaire was reviewed by three nursing education experts for content validity. A pilot study was conducted with 30

students to check clarity and reliability. Cronbach’s alpha coefficient for the overall scale was 0.82, indicating acceptable internal consistency.

Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations) were used to summarize demographic characteristics and responses to questionnaire items. A chi-square tests were applied to assess associated factors (age, gender, year of study, and training in digital literacy) with levels of digital competence. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results:

Out of 384 nursing students, the majority (63.5%) were older than 20 years and in terms of gender, a higher proportion were female (68.7%). By year of study, 21.9% were in the 1st year, while 2nd, 3rd, and 4th year each had around one-quarter of the students. For digital literacy training, majority (74.0%) had no prior digital literacy training. Table I

Table I. Demographic Characteristics of Nursing Students (N = 384)

Variable	Category	N	%
Age	≤ 20 years	140	36.5
	> 20 years	244	63.5
Gender	Male	120	31.3
	Female	264	68.7
Year of Study	1st Year	84	21.9
	2nd year	100	26.0
	3rd year	100	26.0
	4th year	100	26.0
Training in Digital Literacy	Yes	100	26.0
	No	284	74.0

For the use of digital platforms in academics, the highest response was disagreed (36.5%). Regarding online privacy and data protection, the most frequent response was neutral (32.3%). Similarly, awareness of professional guidelines for social media use was also uncertain, with the highest proportion selecting neutral (29.2%). Table II

Table II. Knowledge towards E-Competence among Nursing Students (N = 384)

Items	Strongly Agree n (%)	Agree n (%)	Neutral n (%)	Disagree n (%)	Strongly Disagree n (%)
I know how to use digital platforms for academic purposes.	28 (7.3)	42 (10.9)	110 (28.6)	140 (36.5)	64 (16.7)
I understand online privacy and data protection concepts.	34 (8.9)	60 (15.6)	124 (32.3)	118 (30.7)	48 (12.5)
I am aware of professional guidelines for social media use.	46 (12.0)	80 (20.8)	112 (29.2)	102 (26.6)	44 (11.5)

For online academic searches, the highest response was disagreed (40.6%). For using digital tools in assignments and presentations, the majority also disagreed (44.3%). When asked about evaluating the credibility of online information, the most frequent response was neutral (32.8%). Table III

Table III. Skills towards E- Competence among Nursing Students (N = 384)

Items	Strongly Agree n (%)	Agree n (%)	Neutral n (%)	Disagree n (%)	Strongly Disagree n (%)
I can effectively search for academic information online.	24 (6.3)	38 (9.9)	94 (24.5)	156 (40.6)	72 (18.8)
I can use digital tools for preparing assignments/presentations.	18 (4.7)	32 (8.3)	88 (22.9)	170 (44.3)	76 (19.8)
I can critically evaluate the credibility of online information.	40 (10.4)	66 (17.2)	126 (32.8)	98 (25.5)	54 (14.1)

Majority of the nursing students did not view digital competence as essential for nursing education, with the highest responses being disagreed (45.3%). Confidence in using digital technologies for professional learning was also low, as 39.1% disagreed. Digital tools were not widely recognized as improving communication with peers and faculty, with nearly two-thirds disagreeing (43.8%). Table IV

Table IV. Attitudes toward E- Competence among Nursing Students (N = 384)

Item	Strongly Agree n (%)	Agree n (%)	Neutral n (%)	Disagree n (%)	Strongly Disagree n (%)
I believe digital competence is essential for nursing	12 (3.1)	20 (5.2)	70 (18.2)	174 (45.3)	108 (28.1)

education.					
I feel confident in using digital technologies for professional learning.	22 (5.7)	40 (10.4)	92 (24.0)	150 (39.1)	80 (20.8)
I believe digital tools improve communication with peers and faculty.	16 (4.2)	30 (7.8)	84 (21.9)	168 (43.8)	86 (22.4)

Nearly half (44.8%) of the nursing students exhibited a low level of E -competence with mean domain scores of knowledges 47.4%, skills 45.3%, and attitude 41.7%. **Figure I**

Figure I: Overall E-Competence Score among Nursing Students

Age, gender, year of study, and digital literacy training were significantly ($p < 0.005$) associated with E-competence levels. Older students, males, advanced-year students, and those with digital literacy training showed higher E-competence. **Table V**

Table V. Levels of E-Competence and its Associated factors among Nursing Students (N = 384)

Associated Factors		Level of E-Competence			χ^2	p-value
Items	Categories	Low n (%)	Moderate n (%)	High n (%)		
Age	≤ 20 years	88 (62.9)	38 (27.1)	14 (10.0)	16.84	0.001*
	> 20 years	82 (33.6)	110 (45.1)	52 (21.3)		
Gender	Male	34 (28.3)	52 (43.3)	34 (28.3)	12.62	0.005*
	Female	136 (51.5)	96 (36.4)	32 (12.1)		
Study Year	1st year	50 (59.5)	26 (31.0)	8 (9.5)	42.22	<0.001*
	2nd year	42 (42.0)	38 (38.0)	20 (20.0)		
	3rd year	36 (36.0)	44 (44.0)	20 (20.0)		
	4th year	22 (22.0)	56 (56.0)	42 (42.0)		
Digital Literacy	Yes	20 (20.0)	50 (50.0)	30 (30.0)	30.47	<0.001*
	No	150 (52.8)	98 (34.5)	36 (12.7)		

Training						
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Chi-square test: $p \text{ value} < 0.005$

Discussion

The present study found that nearly half (44.8%) of the nursing students exhibited a low level of E-competence with mean domain scores of knowledge 47.4%, skills 45.3%, and attitude 41.7%. These results highlight a significant gap between the digital demands of clinical practice and the preparedness of graduating nurses. A comparable finding was reported by Raghunathan et al. (2023), who evaluated undergraduate nursing students' informatics competency and found that only 41% of participants achieved a "competent" level. Students performed better in basic information and communication skills but struggled with information and knowledge management, a gap attributed to limited and inconsistent informatics education in nursing curricula (10). Similarly, Le Roux et al. (2024) reported higher scores in computer literacy among South African nursing students but lower competence in clinical information management and information literacy, suggesting that factual knowledge does not always translate into applied skills or professional attitudes. Variability was linked to curricular content, access to simulation, and year of study (11). In contrast, Abou Hashish and Alnajjar (2024) found that Saudi nursing students demonstrated good knowledge, strong digital skills, and positive attitudes, particularly among senior students. These differences may be explained by national digital health initiatives, stronger institutional infrastructure, and sampling of advanced students with greater exposure to clinical information systems (12). Beyond competence measurement, several studies show that digital competence is associated with improved academic outcomes. Leonardsen et al. (2023) reported that students with stronger digital competence were more motivated in courses relying on online platforms (13). Collins (2024) also observed that nursing students with higher digital competence engaged more actively in virtual discussions and group projects,

reflecting deeper learning and stronger collaboration in online environments (14). Together, these studies reinforce the importance of embedding digital tools in nursing education to enhance both academic performance and professional preparedness.

In the present study, age, gender, year of study, and prior digital-literacy training were significantly associated with E-competence. Older students, males, those in advanced years, and students with digital training scored higher. The association between year of study and competence is consistent with earlier evidence showing that senior students report greater digital knowledge and skills, which is largely attributed to increased clinical exposure and curricular progression (12). The role of training is also well established. Reviews of digital-competence education highlight that structured training, integration of digital health in curricula, and hands-on practice with clinical systems improve competence and confidence among nursing students (15,16). Findings on gender and age, however, remain mixed. A multicenter survey of nursing students reported that female students sometimes showed higher technology-related anxiety, which affected their confidence and self-rated competence, whereas males tended to report more confidence in using digital systems (17). Other research among healthcare professionals indicates that age-related differences are domain-specific and often diminish after adjusting for education and work role, suggesting that prior exposure and contextual factors may play a stronger role than chronological age (18). Overall, the present associations are consistent with international evidence: progression through academic years and structured training reliably predict higher e-competence, while gender and age effects vary across contexts. These findings suggest two priorities for nursing education: (a) integrate informatics and digital health systematically across all years of study to provide staged and cumulative skill development, and (b)

offer targeted support, such as workshops and mentoring, to reduce barriers for students who report low confidence or higher digital anxiety.

Conclusion

This study revealed that nearly half (44.8%) of the undergraduate nursing students demonstrated overall low levels of E-competence across knowledge, skills, and attitude domains. Significant associations were observed with age, gender, year of study, and prior digital literacy training. Older students, males, senior-year students, and those with previous digital literacy training scored higher in E-competence.

Recommendations

These findings emphasize the need for structured integration of digital literacy and informatics training throughout the nursing curriculum to strengthen students' preparedness for technology-driven clinical practice and lifelong learning. Hands-on workshops, simulation sessions, and faculty development is essential to strengthen practical skills, while institutional support through improved infrastructure and continuous assessment can ensure equitable access and sustained competence.

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Conflict of Interest: None

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